

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF CONSTRUCTION AND ROAD EQUIPMENT THROUGH THE USE OF MACHINE CONTROL

Ihor Pimonov

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University

Tkachenko Mykhailo

Aspirant, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University

Andrii Yefymenko

Aspirant, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University

Nalia Penkina

Assistant, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University

Yuriy Saliy

Assistant, Head of the Department of Operation, Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University

Abstract

The use of machine monitoring in modern mobile machines is increasingly common on individual machines and in machine sets. Timely monitoring of parameters helps to keep the machine in optimum condition, extend its service life and minimise downtime. The use of automated monitoring and machine control systems greatly simplifies the diagnostic and control process. Machine control significantly improves the quality of hydraulic actuators, making their operation more reliable, efficient and safe. The introduction of such technologies requires an initial investment, but quickly pays for itself through increased equipment life, reduced repair, maintenance and service costs, and increased productivity.

Keywords: increased productivity, increased reliability, efficiency, work operation, machine control, hydraulic drive.

The modern fleet of mobile machines for the construction and maintenance of roads and structures includes a diverse range of types, classifications, manufacturers and machine hours. Machine control elements are increasingly being used on modern mobile machines. Machine control is the process of using special technologies, tools and systems to automatically monitor, analyse and control processes or activities. It is used in various industries, such as manufacturing, construction, transport, etc. Machine control helps to improve product quality, operational accuracy, efficiency and safety. Machine control is based on the use of sensors, controllers, artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms or other technologies that automatically monitor processes (operations) and make decisions without human intervention or with minimal human intervention. These systems are usually integrated into mechanical devices, tools, or software.

During construction work, machine control systems are used for precise levelling of the ground, road paving, as well as for controlling excavators, bulldozers and rollers. One example is GPS control, which provides information on the location and height of the working body, ensuring maximum accuracy during construction work. This makes it possible to use automated quality control systems (for example, using computer vision), constantly monitor parameters (temperature, pressure, speed) in work processes and then use robotic arms controlled by algorithms to perform work operations based on GPS and sensor data.

Machine control includes the basic concepts of logistics processes, putting the machine into autopilot mode, which monitors supply chains in real time using IoT sensors and trackers.

The main components of machine control include:

- sensors that measure various physical parameters such as temperature, pressure, height, speed;
- controllers that process data from sensors and make decisions (for example, PLCs - programmable logic controllers);
- software - AI algorithms, automation systems, mathematical models that analyse the data received;
- drives and mechanisms or actuators that execute commands (for example, a motor that changes the position of a machine).

The advantages of using machine control include

- Improving the accuracy of work performed, eliminating the human factor reduces the number of errors;
- Saving time on the work operation due to automation, which allows you to perform tasks faster than possible manually;
- Improved machine safety, as the use of control systems reduces the risks to workers in hazardous conditions;
- optimization of resources, with precise management reducing material and energy losses;
- the ability to work around the clock without interruption.

However, today's challenges in implementing machine control include the following issues: high cost of implementation, equipment procurement, system

integration and staff training; complexity of maintenance - requiring highly skilled personnel to set up and repair systems; technology dependency - software errors or sensor failures; data security issues - ensuring that systems are protected from cyber attacks.

If you use machines with operational wear and tear or new economic calculations from the introduction of machine control have proven the benefits of its use. That is, the future of machine control will be in integration with the IoT (Internet of Things). All devices and systems will be connected to a single network for real-time data analysis; the use of artificial intelligence will be mandatory, where systems will become "smarter", able to self-learn and make complex decisions without human intervention; autonomous systems will be developed, electronic vision, robots, drones, autonomous cars and other mechanisms will become more independent and efficient.

Optimization of future operation and maintenance thanks to machine monitoring systems enables predictive maintenance based on real-time data. As a result, repairs are carried out when they are actually needed; unnecessary maintenance checks are eliminated, saving time and money, and wear and tear is reduced through more efficient operation. Key benefits for improving the quality of operation are reduced maintenance and repair costs due to timely detection of faults: increased equipment reliability, which minimizes downtime and emergency shutdowns; improved quality of end products, as machines operate more stably and accurately; and accelerated staff training processes, thanks to simulators and remote monitoring systems.

Machine control in construction and road machines is becoming an indispensable tool for improving the quality of operation. The introduction of these technologies requires investment, but in the long run it significantly increases the efficiency, safety and sustainability of equipment.

Let's consider the example of using machine control on a basic machine, and the hydraulic drive of this machine as a separate application. Hydraulic drives are widely used in construction, road, agricultural and mining equipment, where productivity, safety and efficiency depend on their reliable operation.

Improving the quality of hydraulic actuator operation with the help of machine control will be possible through the introduction of modern automation, monitoring and control technologies. Below are the key aspects of using machine control to improve the quality of hydraulic actuators. Continuous monitoring of the hydraulic actuator. Machine control provides continuous collection and analysis of data on the hydraulic actuator's operating parameters:

- Pressure sensors monitor the pressure in the hydraulic system, preventing overloads and water hammer;

- temperature sensors monitor the temperature of the working fluid to avoid overheating and system failure;

- fluid flow sensors - monitor the oil supply and detect leaks;

- vibration sensors - detect abnormalities in the operation of the pump or drive elements, which helps to detect wear on bearings or other components.

Continuous monitoring and analysis of sensor data will ensure timely detection of faults and prevention of emergencies, as well as optimization of hydraulic drive control. The use of additional programmable controllers and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms that will adjust operating parameters depending on the current load (pressure, fluid flow, speed of movement of mechanisms) will prevent peak loads that can lead to accelerated wear of parts and ensure smooth switching on and off of hydraulic drives, reducing the likelihood of water hammer. As an example, in construction equipment such as excavators, hydraulic drives automatically adapt to ground resistance, which improves precision and reduces energy consumption.

In terms of maintenance and timely service of the hydraulic actuator, machine monitoring allows for the implementation of predictive maintenance systems based on sensor data: detection of early signs of component wear (e.g. filters, seals, hydraulic pumps); notification of the need to replace the oil or hydraulic filter before critical situations arise; scheduling maintenance at a convenient time, minimizing machine downtime, resulting in lower repair costs and longer service life of the hydraulic actuators.

The quality of the hydraulic fluid has a direct impact on the operation of the hydraulic actuator. Machine control allows you to: monitor the purity of the oil using contamination sensors (for example, the presence of metal or water particles); analyses the temperature and viscosity of the fluid to ensure optimal operating conditions; automatically block the system if critical contamination levels are exceeded, preventing damage to components. Example: in mobile equipment, the system notifies the operator when oil or filters need to be changed, which prevents the failure of the hydraulic pump and other components.

To improve the control accuracy of machine-controlled hydraulic drives, it is possible to use automatic control systems (for example, using GPS and sensor sensors) that ensure high accuracy of operations, such as asphalt paving or lifting mechanisms. At the same time, stable hydraulic system parameters are maintained to minimize deviations and power losses. The result is increased productivity and reduced energy consumption.

At each stage of operation, machine monitoring systems with automatic diagnostic functions are required: These systems must analyze to determine the causes of performance degradation (e.g. pressure drop due to leakage); record the history of hydraulic actuator parameters for further analysis and improvement of the equipment in a convenient form; and automatically generate reports for maintenance and service operations. For example, in the event of fluid overheating, the system notifies the operator of the possible cause (e.g., a clogged cooling radiator) and offers recommendations for remediation.

Timely troubleshooting prevents accidents by: automatically shutting down the hydraulic drive in the event of a critical drop in oil level or pressure overload;

notifying operators of system malfunctions in real time; and monitoring the safety of the operator and surrounding equipment. For example, in cranes, the hydraulic drive is automatically blocked if sensors detect that the permissible load has been exceeded. There will obviously be resource savings and reduced environmental impact due to automatic control of fluid flows, which reduces oil and energy consumption; minimization of hydraulic fluid leaks, which prevents environmental pollution; timely diagnostics reduces the need for major repairs and replacement of components. For example: hydraulic control systems in road construction equipment allow for precise dosing of the hydraulic fluid flow, ensuring optimum consumption.

The benefits of implementing machine control for hydraulic actuators include

- Increased component life due to optimal operating conditions;
- Reduced operating costs due to the prevention of breakdowns and leaks.
- Increased reliability and reduced downtime of equipment;
- Increased operational safety for operators and the environment;
- optimization of productivity through precise process control.

Timely monitoring of these parameters helps to maintain the hydraulic drive in optimal condition, increase its service life and minimize downtime. The use of automated monitoring and machine control systems (sensors, controllers) greatly simplifies the diagnostic and control process. Machine control significantly improves the quality of hydraulic actuators, making their operation more reliable, efficient and safe. The introduction of such technologies requires an initial investment, but quickly pays for itself by increasing the service life of the equipment, reducing repair, maintenance and service costs, and increasing productivity. The introduction of machine control is gradually transforming various industries, making processes more efficient, safer and more affordable.

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